

Structural Properties of Cationic Surfactant-Fatty Alcohol Bilayers: Insights from Dissipative Particle Dynamics[†]

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Bilayers, self-assembled by cationic surfactants and fatty alcohols in water, are the basic units of lamellar gel networks – creamy formulations extensively used in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. Mesoscopic modelling and study of the bilayers formed by single- or double-tail cationic surfactants (CTAC or DHDAC), and fatty alcohols (FAs) in the lamellar fluid and gel phases were employed. Fatty alcohols with alkyl tail equal to or greater than the surfactant alkyl tail, i.e., C₁₆FA or C₁₈FA and C₂₂FA, were considered. A model formulation was explored with the FA concentration greater than that of the surfactant and the structure of the fluid and gel bilayers in tensionless state characterised via the density profiles across the bilayers, orientational order parameters of the surfactant and FA chains, intrinsic analysis of the bilayer interfaces, and bending rigidity. The intrinsic analysis allows identification and quantification of the coexistence of the interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases present within the gel bilayers. The FA chains were found to conform the primary scaffolding of the bilayers while the surfactant chains tessellate bilayer monolayers from their water-hydrophobic interface. Further, the overlap of the FA chains from the apposed monolayers of the fluid bilayers rises with increasing FA length. Finally, the prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase within the gel bilayers becomes enhanced upon the FA length increase with a preference of the surfactant chains to reside in the non-interdigitated phase rather than the interdigitated phase.

1 Introduction

Fatty alcohols (FAs) combined with quaternary ammonium surfactants such as cetyltrimethylammonium chloride (CTAC) are common ingredients in creamy formulations, such as conditioners.¹ In these conditioner formulations, the cationic surfactant concentration is typically of the order of 1-5% with the FA concentration greater than that of the surfactant. Aqueous dispersions of surfactants and FAs lead to the formation of lamellar gel networks, percolating structures that can withstand elastic deformation, and are mainly composed of lamellar rigid (L_{β}) phase and bulk water. The lamellar phase consists of surfactant and FA bilayers spaced by inter-lamellar aqueous layers. Therefore, the

L_{β} bilayers are the basic units of the lamellar gel networks.² However in formulated gel-phases, the different components are first mixed together at high enough temperatures where fluid (L_{α}) bilayers are formed.³

Molecular modelling has become a complementary tool to experiments, exploring ways to characterise the self-assembly of various amphiphilic systems via the choice of surfactants, FAs, and solvent as well as the surfactant and FA architecture.^{4,5} However, the time and length scales for self-assembly in complex amphiphilic systems are too long to be conveniently studied by all-atom molecular dynamics.^{6–8} Instead, researchers are increasingly adopting mesoscopic modelling, such as coarse-grain molecular dynamics⁹ or dissipative particle dynamics (DPD).^{10,11} These methods employ coarse-grain models where molecules or molecular fragments are grouped into mesoscopic beads.¹² The DPD method has been proved to be an effective and flexible modelling tool and has been used to address a wide range of mesoscale problems in and out of equilibrium.^{13–18}

DPD simulations have been extensively used for studying bilayers, mainly biological (lipid) membranes,^{19–24} including the effect of alcohols on membrane structures.^{22,25} DPD simulations of bilayers have typically employed generic DPD models with beads

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of the same size and bead-bead interaction parameters linked to χ -parameters in the Flory-Huggins-type model. Recently, Anderson et al.²⁶ developed a transferable DPD force field (FF) which allows more realistic treatment of FAs and non-ionic surfactants than the generic DPD models. The FF first considered beads of a different size derived from their experimental liquid volume. Second, the bead-bead interaction parameters of the FF were calibrated against experimental water-octanol partition coefficients. Finally, the bonded interactions of the FF were adjusted to realistically reproduce the distances between groups corresponding to DPD beads. Later, Anderson et al.²⁷ suggested a pragmatic approach to parameterise charged beads within the transferable DPD FF and justified the charged-bead parametrisation by comparing critical micelle concentrations (CMCs) of ionic surfactants against experimental values. Therefore, the generic DPD FF^{26,27} leads to a prediction of the self-assembled behaviour in surfactant-based systems which allows screening of the surfactant-system formulations.^{28–30}

The L_α bilayers at high temperatures become a key determinant for the formation of the lamellar gel networks whereas the L_β bilayers are the fundamental building blocks of the gel phases, and their structure determines the macroscopic properties such as viscosity. The current capability of DPD (especially efficient computing time) is amenable to capture the properties of one bilayer within a simulation box. For the purposes of exploring the fundamental properties of the bilayer, this represents an order of magnitude of detailed “magnification” relative to the unit size accessible by crystallographic methods, e.g., Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) or Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS), as box-sizes can be accommodated to match the typical d -spacing sizes. The d -spacing corresponds to the smallest repeat unit of the lamellar phase, composed by one bilayer and one water layer and is typically determined experimentally by crystallographic methods such as SAXS, and examination of the ratio amongst diffraction peaks. Since box-sizes in DPD simulations are set to match typical d -spacings in the range of nm, DPD thus leads to an improvement in detail at angstrom resolution.

Experimentally, the interpretation of SAXS and WAXS data is limited, e.g., WAXS provides unequivocal evidence of the type of surfactant packing (e.g., hexagonal or orthorhombic) and SAXS provides the d -spacing. However, if a surfactant with a different molecular architecture is used at subtle inclusion levels, both quantities can remain unchanged, especially for lamellar phases. The temptation is then to use these measurements for understanding changes at the bilayer length scale, when on occasion the interpretation tends to be based on inference rather than direct evidence. It would be useful for the scientist to access more detail at the bilayer level, such that, at least in principle, the effect of the chemistry on the morphology can be monitored with a higher degree of confidence. There are alternative measurements to answer these questions, such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) but these require surfactant deuteration, which pushes the experimentalist to consider cost, speed, availability and relevance, amongst other issues. The “cartoon pictures”, well known in crystallography and colloids science literature, have been generated using the available evidence but with limitations, and leave

gaps in the detail with potential significance.

In this work, we have investigated the structural properties of the fluid and gel bilayers, self-assembled by cationic surfactants CTAC or dihexadecyldimethylammonium chloride (DHDAC), and C_{16} FA or C_{18} FA and/or C_{22} FA in water. We employed DPD with the generic DPD FF of Anderson et al.,^{26,27} augmented by the bond-bond repulsive interactions to avoid topology violations.³¹ The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 outlines the methodology, including the DPD method, coarse-grain models, simulation details, and the definitions of bilayers properties. In Section 3, we present and discuss our results with a summary and concluding remarks in Section 4.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dissipative Particle Dynamics

Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD) is a mesoscopic model that treats groups of atoms or molecular fragments as single beads; in the standard DPD, as beads of the same size.^{32–34} In this work following Anderson et al.,²⁶ we employ coarse-grain models with different bead sizes, enhancing realism when compared to the standard DPD.

We employed the DPD units, introduced using m_0 , kT_0 and r_c as units of mass, energy, and length, respectively, where m_0 is the mass of a solvent bead, k is the Boltzmann constant, T_0 is the reference temperature, and r_c is the cut-off distance. Then, short-range bead-bead interactions are described by a soft-sphere repulsive potential

$$u_{ij}^{\text{sr}} = \begin{cases} \frac{a_{ij}}{2} R_{ij} \left(1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{R_{ij}}\right)^2 & r_{ij} \leq R_{ij} \\ 0 & r_{ij} > R_{ij} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $a_{ij} \leftarrow a_{ij}r_c/(kT_0)$ is the maximum repulsion between the interacting beads, $r_{ij} \leftarrow r_{ij}/r_c$ is their separation, $r_{ij} = |\mathbf{r}_{ij}|$, $\mathbf{r}_{ij} = \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j$, and $R_{ij} \leftarrow R_{ij}/r_c$ is the bead size parameter. The repulsion parameter a_{ij} is proportional to the Flory-Huggins interaction parameter, χ_{ij} :

$$\chi_{ij} = C_{\text{FH-DPD}} \left(a_{ij}R_{ij}^3 - \frac{a_{ii}R_{ii}^3 + a_{jj}R_{jj}^3}{2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $C_{\text{FH-DPD}}$ is the proportionality constant; e.g., in the standard DPD, $C_{\text{FH-DPD}} \simeq 0.3$.³⁴ Eq. (2) indicates that attraction between the interacting beads is treated as weaker repulsion than repulsions between the like beads.

The cationic surfactant head carries a positive charge $q_h = +1e$ while the counter-ion (CI) bears a negative charge $q_{\text{CI}} = -1e$. The bead-bead electrostatic interactions in DPD require that the charges must be spread out over a finite volume using a smeared charge distribution $\rho_q(r)$ to prevent the divergence of the electrostatic potential and to avoid collapse of unlike point charges on top of each other.^{35–37} We employ a Gaussian smeared charge distribution³⁸

$$\rho_q(r) = q \left(\frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_G} \right)^{3/2} \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma_G^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where σ_G is the length scale of the charge q . The interaction between charged DPD beads i and j is then

$$u_{ij}^{\text{el}} = \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{r_{ij}}{2\sigma_G}\right) \quad (4)$$

where $q_\alpha \leftarrow q_\alpha / \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon_r r_c kT_0}$ and $\sigma_G \leftarrow \sigma_G / r_c$; ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity and ϵ_r is the dielectric constant. It is worth mentioning that a popular Slater-type (exponential) smeared charge distribution $\rho_q(r) = \frac{q}{\pi\lambda^3} \exp(-\frac{2r}{\lambda})$ (λ is the charge decay length) provides essentially the same results as the Gaussian smeared charge distribution if the whole charged is localised within a DPD bead,³⁷ see also Appendix A for comparison of the Gaussian and exponential smeared charge distributions.

To model surfactants and FAs, DPD beads are connected into chains with a simple harmonic potential

$$u^{\text{bond}} = \frac{K_b}{2} (r - r_0)^2 \quad (5)$$

which represents bonds between connected DPD beads. In Eq. (5), $K_b \leftarrow K_b r_c^2 / (kT_0)$ is the bond constant, $r \leftarrow r / r_c$ is the distance between the connected beads, and $r_0 \leftarrow r_0 / r_c$ is the nominal bond length. Chain rigidity is introduced using a harmonic angular potential

$$u^{\text{bend}} = \frac{K_a}{2} (\theta - \theta_0)^2 \quad (6)$$

between pairs of bonds. In Eq. (6), $K_a \leftarrow K_a / (kT_0)$ is the bending constant, θ and θ_0 are, respectively, the angle and nominal angle between the pairs of bonds. Conservative forces, \mathbf{F}^C , $C \equiv (\text{sr}, \text{el}, \text{bond}, \text{bend})$, are then defined as a negative derivative of corresponding interaction potentials, $\mathbf{F}^C = -(du^C/dr)\mathbf{e}$, where $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{r}/r$ is the unit separation vector.

The use of DPD chain models with soft-sphere repulsive potentials allows unphysical crossing of the chains (topology violations). We augmented the generic DPD FF with the modified segmental repulsive potential (mSRP) to suppress the chain crossing.³¹ The mSRP acts between pairs of bonds. A force acting between bonds k and l , separated by the distance d_{kl} , is

$$\mathbf{F}_{kl}^{\text{SRP}} = b \left(1 - \frac{d_{kl}}{d_c}\right) \frac{\mathbf{d}_{kl}}{d_{kl}} \quad (7)$$

where $d_{kl} \leftarrow d_{kl} / r_c$, $d_{kl} = |\mathbf{d}_{kl}|$, $\mathbf{d}_{kl} = \mathbf{d}_k - \mathbf{d}_l$, $b \leftarrow b r_c / (kT_0)$ is the bond-bond force constant, and $d_c \leftarrow d_c / r_c$ is the bond-bond cut-off distance. The force acting on a bond given by Eq. (7) is decomposed into bead forces according to the lever rule. For beads i and j in bond k :

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{\text{SRP}} = \mathbf{F}_{kl}^{\text{SRP}} \cdot L \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_j^{\text{SRP}} = \mathbf{F}_{kl}^{\text{SRP}} \cdot (1 - L) \quad (9)$$

where L determines the weighting of the force on each bead.³¹ Although the mSRP potential is traditionally used to simulate entanglements for long polymers, here it is employed to help to faithfully capture a nematic order of hydrophobic tails within gel phases. On the one hand, the bond-bond repulsions only slightly affect the fluid bilayers in comparison with the DPD simulations

without the mSRP potential which is due to the surfactant and FA chain lengths, and high beads mobility. On the other hand, a combination of lower beads mobility and suppression of the chain crossing results in stretching of the surfactant and FA chains and ordering their hydrophobic tails in the gel bilayers. Without the mSRP potential, the surfactant and FA chains would exhibit less pronounced chain stretching and ordering in the gel bilayers.

Generally, coarse-graining causes a loss of friction and ‘‘smoothing’’ of the free-energy landscape, leading to faster dynamics at the mesoscale level.³⁹ In DPD, the loss of friction can be effectively returned to the system using pair-wise dissipative and random forces

$$\mathbf{F}_{ij}^D = -\tilde{\gamma}_{ij} \omega(r_{ij})^2 (\mathbf{v}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{e}_{ij}) \mathbf{e}_{ij} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{ij}^R = \tilde{\sigma}_{ij} \omega(r_{ij}) \frac{\zeta_{ij}}{\sqrt{\Delta t}} \mathbf{e}_{ij} \quad (11)$$

respectively. In Eqs. (10) and (11), $\mathbf{v}_{ij} = \mathbf{p}_i / m_i - \mathbf{p}_j / m_j$, $m_\alpha \leftarrow m_\alpha / m_0$ and \mathbf{p}_α are, respectively, the mass and momentum of a bead α , ζ_{ij} is a Gaussian random number with zero mean and unit variance, $\Delta t \leftarrow \Delta t \sqrt{kT_0 / m_0} / r_c$ is the time step, $\tilde{\gamma}_{ij} \leftarrow \tilde{\gamma}_{ij} r_c / \sqrt{m_0 kT_0}$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}$ are, respectively, the friction coefficient and noise amplitude for the interacting beads, and $\omega(r_{ij})$ is a weighting function.

The friction coefficient and noise amplitude are related via the fluctuation-dissipation theorem³³

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{ij}^2 = 2T\tilde{\gamma}_{ij} \quad (12)$$

where $T \leftarrow T / T_0$ and T is the system temperature. The weighting function is typically given by

$$\omega(r_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{R_{ij}} & r_{ij} \leq R_{ij} \\ 0 & r_{ij} > R_{ij} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The dissipative and random forces act together as a thermostat, and along with the conservative forces they also guarantee local momentum conservation and ensure correct hydrodynamic behaviour.

2.2 Coarse-Grain Models

To model aqueous solutions of CTAC or DHDAC and C_n FA, we employ the transferable DPD FF,²⁶ combined with the pragmatic approach to parametrise the charged beads within the transferable DPD FF.²⁷ This was augmented by the bond-bond repulsive potential (6) to avoid topology violations.³¹ The transferable DPD FF²⁶ was developed by a systematic top-down thermodynamic parametrisation using water-octanol partition coefficients, supplemented by water-octanol phase equilibria and pure liquid phase density data. DPD beads in the FF represent either two water molecules (a solvent bead) or molecular fragments comprising several ‘‘heavy atoms’’, i.e., C, O and N for the systems studied in this work.

First, following Groot and Warren,³⁴ the FF asserts that the density of liquid water corresponds to the bead number density $\rho \leftarrow \rho r_c^3 = 3$. Then, the use of the molecular volume of liquid water ($V_m = 30 \text{ \AA}^3$ ⁴⁰), number density ($\rho = 3$), and

Fig. 1 Coarse-grain models of (a) CTAC and (b) DHDAC surfactants, and (c) C₁₆FA (hexadecanol). Key: c≡[CH₃]; c2≡[CH₂]; cc≡[CH₂CH₂]; co≡[CH₂OH]; h1≡[(CH₃)₃N⁺CH₂]; h2≡[(CH₃)₂N⁺]; Cl≡[Cl⁻].

two water molecules per solvent bead ($N_m = 2$) results in $r_c \approx 5.65$ Å. Second, the FF constructs molecules of interest from connected beads comprising alkyl, alcohol, and alkyl ammonium (with $q_h = +1e$) molecular fragments. By denoting $c \equiv [\text{CH}_3]$, $c2 \equiv [\text{CH}_2]$, $cc \equiv [\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2]$, $co \equiv [\text{CH}_2\text{OH}]$, $h1 \equiv [(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2]$, $h2 \equiv [(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}^+]$, and $\text{Cl} \equiv [\text{Cl}^-]$, CTAC and DHDAC surfactants can then be represented as $\text{cl}/h1\text{-cc}_7\text{-c}$ and $\text{cl}/h2\text{-(c2-cc}_7\text{-c)}_2$, respectively, and $C_n\text{FA}$ as $\text{co-cc}_n\text{-c}$, where $n = 7, 8$ and 10 . Fig. 1 shows coarse-grain models of both cationic surfactants and a FA. The surfactant head beads $h1$ and $h2$ contain five and three heavy atoms, respectively, which make them bulkier in comparison with other DPD beads. Nevertheless, a similar coarse-graining was recently employed to represent the charged head of the SLES surfactant (five heavy atoms in a bead)⁴¹ or non-charged amide fragments of amide surfactants (six heavy atoms in a bead)⁴² within the generic DPD FF.^{26,27} Alternatively, the CTAC or DHDAC heads can be coarse-grained using smaller molecular fragments; e.g., $h1$ as a charged $[\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2]$ bead tightly bonded with three $[\text{CH}_3]$ beads. However, due to a short r_0 between $[\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2]$ and $[\text{CH}_3]$ beads, and bead-bead soft repulsive interactions, assembly of the $[\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2]$ bead and three $[\text{CH}_3]$ beads effectively acts similarly as the bulky $h1$ bead.

The values of R_{ii} for the beads are determined from their molar volume, $V_{m,i}$, listed in Table 1. The FF considers that $R_{ii}^3 \propto V_{m,i}$ with the proportionality constant set by the water bead mapping; therefore, $R_{ii} = (V_{m,i}/V_{m,(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2})^{1/3}$. Then, the values of R_{ij} are given by the arithmetic mixing rule as $R_{ij} = (R_{ii} + R_{jj})/2$ which is equivalent to assigning an effective radius $R_\alpha = R_{\alpha\alpha}/2$ to individual beads and to assert that $R_{ij} = R_i + R_j$. The values of a_{ii} for the water, and alkyl and alcohol beads (uncharged DPD beads) are adjusted, respectively, to match the experimental compressibility of liquid water and experimental densities of various simple molecular liquids containing the relevant molecular frag-

ments. Starting from $a_{ij} = (a_{ii} + a_{jj})/2$, the FF then adjusts the values of a_{ij} for the uncharged DPD beads to fit the experimental water-octanol partition coefficients.⁴³

To parametrise the charged DPD beads ($h1 \equiv [(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2]$ and $h2 \equiv [(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}^+]$ with $q_h = +1e$, and $\text{Cl} \equiv [\text{Cl}^-]$ with $q_{\text{Cl}} = -1e$), we followed the pragmatic approach of Anderson et al.²⁷ with the details provided in Appendix A. Then similarly as Anderson et al.²⁷, we justified reliability of our determined R_{ij} and a_{ij} parameters for the charged DPD beads by simulating the CMC of an ionic surfactant, specifically the C₁₂TAB surfactant, without the bond-bond repulsive potential (6). The C₁₂TAB has the same charged head as CTAC but it is shorter than CTAC, making simulation of the CMC easier and, in addition, experimental values of its CMC are readily available.⁴⁴ The chlorine Cl is modelled as a partially hydrated ion, consisting of a Cl atom and two water molecules.²⁷ All nonbonded interaction parameters are summarised in Table 1, including the Flory-Huggins parameters, χ_{ij} , given by Eq. (2) with $C_{\text{FH-DPD}} = 0.3$ for the standard DPD.³⁴

The bonded interactions involve pairwise bonds, augmented by three-body angular potentials to confer additional rigidity to the system structures. First instead of adjusting of the nominal bond length to reproduce the true experimental or atomistic-simulation distances between molecular groups, Anderson et al.²⁶ have shown that the number of heavy atoms in a bead can be used to estimate realistic values of r_0 for linear molecules. Therefore with the bond constant $K_b = 150$, choice guided by atomistic simulations, the FF sets the nominal bond length $r_0 = 0.39$ for bonds between beads that each contain two heavy atoms (e.g., cc-cc); for bonds involving beads with additional heavy atoms (e.g., cc-coc), 0.1 is added to $r_0 = 0.39$ while for bonds involving beads with fewer heavy atoms (e.g., cc-c), 0.1 is subtracted from $r_0 = 0.39$; $\text{coc} \equiv [\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_2]$. The nominal bond length $r_0 = 0.39$ corresponds to 2.52 Å which is approximately equivalent to the distance between the centres of two alkane beads, each with two heavy atoms. This pragmatic approach of assigning values of r_0 between different DPD beads reproduce reasonably well the real distances between molecular groups at the mesoscopic level.^{26,41} Note that the approach needs to take into account that due to the non-bonded repulsion between bonded beads, the average distance within a DPD simulation differs from the value of r_0 in the bond potential (5).

Second for bending interactions, the FF employs the bending constant $K_a = 5$, choice guided by atomistic simulations,⁴¹ and the nominal angle between the pairs of bonds $\theta_0 = 180^\circ$. No bending interaction was employed for the angle between the two DHDAC tails. The bending potential (6) together with the values of K_a and θ_0 becomes an important element of rigidity of small molecules such as surfactants or FAs since, e.g., surfactant or FA tail stiffness directly controls the surfactant or FA effective length and area-per-molecule,⁴⁵ which in turn both affect the surfactant and FA packing and self-assembly.⁴⁶

For the bond-bond mSRP interactions, we employ the standard values of $b = 100$ and $d_c = 0.8$ which suppress the topological violations by about four orders relative to the standard DPD and do not significantly alter the system potential energy and pressure relative to the standard DPD.³¹

Table 1 The values of the size parameter, $R_{ij} \leftarrow R_{ij}/r_c$, molar volume, $V_{m,i}$, maximum repulsion, $a_{ij} \leftarrow a_{ij}r_c/(kT_0)$, mass, $m_i \leftarrow m_i/m_0$, and Flory-Huggins parameter, χ_{ij} , for all DPD beads; $r_c = 5.65 \text{ \AA}$ is the cut-off distance, $T_0 = 330 \text{ K}$ is the reference temperature, m_0 is the mass of the reference bead corresponding to the water bead with two water molecules, and k is the Boltzmann constant. The chlorine counter-ion (Cl) is modelled as a partially hydrated ion, consisting of a Cl atom and two water molecules. Further, the Cl is treated as the water bead with the charge $q_{Cl} = -1e$. Key: $w \equiv [(H_2O)_2]$; $c \equiv [CH_3]$; $c2 \equiv [CH_2]$; $cc \equiv [CH_2CH_2]$; $co \equiv [CH_2OH]$; $h1 \equiv [(CH_3)_3N^+CH_2]$; $h2 \equiv [(CH_3)_2N^+]$.

	R_{ij}						$V_{m,i}$ (cm ³ /mol)	
	w	c	c2	cc	co	h1		h2
w	1.0000						36.0	
c	0.9775	0.9550					33.9	
c2	0.9626	0.9401	0.9251				28.5	
cc	1.0370	1.0145	0.9996	1.0740			44.6	
co	0.9900	0.9675	0.9526	1.0270	0.9800		33.9	
h1	1.1825	1.1600	–	1.2195	1.1725	1.3650	91.5	
h2	1.0801	1.0576	1.0426	1.1171	1.0701	–	1.1601	56.2
	a_{ij}						m_i	
	w	c	c2	cc	co	h1		h2
w	25.0						1.00	
c	45.0	24.0					0.42	
c2	45.0	24.0	24.0				0.39	
cc	45.0	23.0	23.0	22.0			0.78	
co	14.5	26.0	26.0	26.0	14.0		0.86	
h1	15.0	28.5	–	28.5	25.0	10.0	2.03	
h2	19.8	28.5	28.5	28.5	25.0	–	16.0	1.22
	χ_{ij}							
	w	c	c2	cc	co	h1		h2
w	0							
c	5.7	0						
c2	5.4	0	0					
cc	7.2	0	0	0				
co	-1.5	2.0	1.9	2.4	0			
h1	-0.1	6.4	–	7.6	6.3	0		
h2	1.4	4.6	4.5	5.5	4.9	–	0	

2.3 Simulation Details

We performed DPD simulations at $\rho = 3$ and two temperatures, $T = 1.0$. We neglected the dependence of the interaction parameters on temperature since it is rather weak.⁴⁷ We observed that at $T = 1.0$, bilayers were in a fluid state while at $T = 0.7$, they were in a gel phase. Typically for aqueous CTAC-FA solutions, a lamellar fluid phase exists above a temperature of 320 K and a lamellar gel phase below this temperature.^{5,48} To translate the DPD temperature to physical temperature we thus ad hoc linked $T = 0.7$ with a temperature of 300 K and $T = 1.0$ with a temperature of 330 K, which then sets $T_0 = 330 \text{ K}$.²²

If not constrained, a bilayer adopts the configuration corresponding to the lowest free energy, i.e., a tensionless state (a state with the zero interfacial tension).²¹ The interfacial tension, γ , can be measured using the mechanical route⁴⁹ as

$$\gamma \leftarrow \frac{\gamma r_c^2}{kT_0} = \frac{L_z}{2} \left(\langle P_{zz} \rangle - \frac{\langle P_{xx} \rangle + \langle P_{yy} \rangle}{2} \right) \quad (14)$$

where L_z is the box length in the z -direction, $P_{\alpha\alpha}$ is the diagonal component of the pressure tensor, and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the ensemble average.⁵⁰ To ensure that both the fluid and gel bilayers are simulated at the minimum of the system free energy we applied the box-length-search algorithm.⁵¹ Starting from initial box lengths L_x , L_y , and L_z the box-length-search algorithm iteratively finds the box lengths that minimise the system free energy while maintaining constant system volume (constant system density). Due to the sufficiently large values of L_x and L_y employed, we have restricted the box-length-search algorithm to maintain the same

box length in the two dimensions parallel to the bilayer interface, i.e., $L_x = L_y$ and their increments $\Delta L_x = \Delta L_y$. The change in the system free energy associated with ΔL_x is

$$\Delta A = -\frac{2Z}{P} \left(\frac{\langle P_{xx} \rangle + \langle P_{yy} \rangle}{2} - \langle P_{zz} \rangle \right) \frac{\Delta L_x}{L_x} \quad (15)$$

where Z is the compressibility factor and P is the system pressure.⁵¹ Then, the box-length-search algorithm relies on a series of DPD simulations where L_x is successively adjusted (increased or decreased) by ΔL_x against the running average of γ until the zero value of γ is reached, practically $\gamma = 0 \pm 0.1$. The adjustment of L_x is carried out by keeping the box volume fixed (L_z follows from constraint of the fixed box volume), and the values of ΔL_x are determined via the secant method.⁵² The resulting box lengths L_x , L_y , and L_z , for which $\langle P_{xx} \rangle = \langle P_{yy} \rangle = \langle P_{zz} \rangle$ within statistical uncertainties and which correspond to the minimum of the system free energy, are employed in DPD production runs.

The DPD simulations of both the fluid and gel bilayers started from a pre-assembled bilayer in a rectangular simulation box with the bilayer perpendicular to the z -direction. The pre-assembled bilayer consists of two apposed, non-interdigitated monolayers with the surfactant and FA chains aligned along the z -direction and randomly, and uniformly distributed within each monolayer. Further, the surfactant and FA head beads were located at water-monolayer interfaces, and CIs were close to the surfactant head beads in the water layer. The initial box lengths L_x , L_y , and L_z of the pre-assembled bilayer were chosen by trial and error not to drastically differ from the final values of L_x , L_y , and L_z found by

the box-length-search algorithm. The pre-assembled bilayer was then equilibrated followed first by application of the box-length-search algorithm and then by production run. Such the starting configurations along with the box-length-search algorithm facilitate rapid attainment of the equilibrium state at the minimum of the system free energy.

We employed the Ewald sum⁵⁰ to treat the long-range bead-bead electrostatic interactions with $\sigma_G = 0.18$, $\epsilon_r = 80$ (corresponding to the dielectric constant of liquid water), Ewald real-space convergence parameter equal to $1/(2\sigma_G)$, and Ewald reciprocal-space vector cut-off equal to 27. This value of σ_G guarantees that the whole charge is localised within a DPD bead³⁷ while the choice of the Ewald real-space convergence parameter reduces all terms in the real space (energy, force, and virial) to zero.⁵³ For the exponential smeared charge distribution, the equivalent value to $\sigma_G = 0.18$ is $\lambda = 0.2$.³⁷

We used about 150,000 DPD beads in the rectangular simulation box of $L_x = L_y \simeq (30 - 37)r_c$ and $L_z \simeq (35 - 44)r_c$, with periodic boundary conditions in all directions. A DPD simulation run of a tensionless bilayer spanned from 1M to 5M time steps, including an equilibration period of about 0.5M time steps. DPD trajectories were generated using the LAMMPS simulation package,⁵⁴ followed by post-processing using in-house codes to evaluate the bilayer properties. We further employed $\Delta t = 0.01$ and $\bar{\gamma} \equiv \bar{\gamma}_{ij} = 4.5$ which may affect the estimate of time in real units based on $\Delta t \leftarrow \Delta t r_c / \sqrt{kT_0/m_0}$. Instead, one may follow Groot and Rabone⁵⁵ and gauge the physical unit of time τ by matching the experimental self-diffusivity of water, D_w^{exp} , with that of DPD model water, D_w^{DPD} , which leads to

$$\tau = \frac{N_m D_w^{\text{DPD}} r_c^2}{D_w^{\text{exp}}} \quad (16)$$

where $N_m = 2$ in this work, $D_w^{\text{exp}} = 2.30 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$,⁵⁶ and $D_w^{\text{DPD}} = 0.3$.⁵⁷ Eq. (16) gives $\tau \simeq 80$ ps and in turn, $\Delta t \simeq 0.9$ ps.

2.4 Bilayers Properties

In this section, we define the quantities used to characterise the bilayer phases.^{22,58}

2.4.1 Density Profiles

Density profiles along the z -direction were evaluated to elucidate density behaviour within the bilayer phases. They were computed for water, CI, surfactant and FA heads and tails as well as for the individual surfactant and FA beads. A number density profile of a bead α is defined as

$$\rho_\alpha(z) = \frac{\sum_i \delta(z - z_i^\alpha)}{\Delta z L_x L_y} \quad (17)$$

where $\sum_i \delta(z - z_i^\alpha)$ gives the number of α beads inside a slice of the simulation box of the thickness Δz along the z -axis. The mass density profiles can then be obtained by multiplying $\rho_\alpha(z)$ with bead molecular weights.

2.4.2 Orientational Order Parameters

Orientational order parameters quantify the ordering of surfactant and FA chains within the bilayer. The orientational order parameters were evaluated for the whole chains as well as for individual chain bonds. The overall orientational order parameter is given by

$$S = \frac{3 \cos^2 \theta - 1}{2} \quad (18)$$

where θ is the angle between the vector, connecting the first and last tail beads, and the bilayer normal: $\cos \theta = z_{\text{cc}_1/c_2,c}/r_{\text{cc}_1/c_2,c}$; $r_{\text{cc}_1/c_2,c} = |\mathbf{r}_{\text{cc}_1/c_2,c}|$ and $\mathbf{r}_{\text{cc}_1/c_2,c} = \mathbf{r}_{\text{cc}_1/c_2} - \mathbf{r}_c$; see Fig. 1 for bead notation. The local orientational order parameter of a bond n is defined as

$$S_n = \frac{3 \cos^2 \theta_{n,n+1} - 1}{2} \quad (19)$$

where $\theta_{n,n+1}$ is the angle between the bond vector and the bilayer normal: $\cos \theta_{n,n+1} = z_{n,n+1}/r_{n,n+1}$; $r_{n,n+1} = |\mathbf{r}_{n,n+1}|$, $\mathbf{r}_{n,n+1} = \mathbf{r}_n - \mathbf{r}_{n+1}$, and \mathbf{r}_n and \mathbf{r}_{n+1} are bead positions along the tail bonds. The S_n provides an indication of the persistence of the orientational order through the bilayer. Values of S or S_n vary between -0.5 and 1 ; values close to -0.5 and 1 indicate that the chains become perpendicular and parallel, respectively, with respect to the bilayer normal. A random orientation of chains corresponds to the value of S or S_n equal to 0.25 , i.e., $\cos^2 \theta$ or $\cos^2 \theta_{n,n+1}$ ranging uniformly between zero and unity.⁵⁹

2.4.3 Chain Overlap and Interdigitation

To investigate the presence of an interdigitated phase and the extent of interpenetration of the hydrophobic tails of surfactants or FAs on the apposed monolayers of the bilayer, the chain overlap is defined as

$$D_{\text{overlap}} = 2 \frac{L_t^{(1)} + L_t^{(2)} - D_c}{L_t^{(1)} + L_t^{(2)}} \quad (20)$$

In Eq. (20), $L_t^{(1)}$ and $L_t^{(2)}$ are the tail lengths in the direction normal to the monolayers (1) and (2), respectively: $L_t^{(1)} = |z_{\text{cc}_1^{(1)}/c_2^{(1)}} - z_c^{(1)}|$ and $L_t^{(2)} = |z_{\text{cc}_1^{(2)}/c_2^{(2)}} - z_c^{(2)}|$, and D_c is the thickness of the hydrophobic core, defined as the distance along the bilayer normal between the first tail bead of a surfactant/FA in one monolayer (1) and that in the apposed monolayer (2): $D_c = |z_{\text{cc}_1/c_2}^{(1)} - z_{\text{cc}_1/c_2}^{(2)}|$; see below additional details about determination of $L_t^{(1)}$, $L_t^{(2)}$, and D_c . The value of $D_{\text{overlap}} = 1$ corresponds to the complete interpenetration of the tails. Values of D_{overlap} between zero and unity indicate partial interpenetration of the tails while $D_{\text{overlap}} < 0$ corresponds to no tails interpenetration.

2.4.4 Bilayer Thickness and Intrinsic Analysis

Due to the presence of bilayer undulations, evaluation of the bilayer thickness, h_{lam} , is not a straightforward task. Traditionally, h_{lam} is determined as the distance between peaks in density profiles of the surfactant and FA heads. Alternatively, h_{lam} can be obtained as the difference between ensemble averages of z -positions of the surfactant and FA heads in apposed monolayers. This is reasonable for fluid bilayers due to the symmetry of the density profiles but it becomes questionable for gel bilayers which may consist of a mixture of interdigitated and non-interdigitated

phases with different bilayer thicknesses. Alternatively, h_{lam} can be obtained via an intrinsic analysis which allows identification of the instantaneous location of the interface, at the mesoscopic level, for each bilayer configuration and then determining properties, including h_{lam} , relative to this location. The intrinsic analysis eliminates the broadening of the interface caused by the bilayer undulations and enables the computing of various properties relative to this intrinsic surface rather than to the macroscopically planar Gibbs dividing surface.^{60,61}

We employed the intrinsic method of Identification of the Truly Interfacial Molecules (ITIM),^{62,63} which is based on moving fictitious probe spheres of a given radius along straight lines that are perpendicular to the bilayer interface, starting from the aqueous phase. The size of the surfactant and FA beads was approximated by their size parameters R_{ii} . Once the fictitious probe sphere touches the first bead of the surfactants or FAs it is stopped, and the touched bead is marked as being interfacial. Once the probe sphere is moved along all test lines the full list of the truly interfacial DPD beads is identified. The bilayer surface is then approximated by the set of the intersection points of the probe spheres with the test lines along which they are moved, at the position where the probe spheres were stopped. We used a probe radius of $1r_c$ and the test lines were arranged with the spacing $1r_c$ along the xy -plane.

The surface points on both sides of the bilayer along with their 2D interpolation⁵² make it possible to compute the values of the bilayer thickness along the xy -plane and, in turn, to determine the bilayer thickness distribution. A bilayer thickness at an $[x, y]$ -point is given as the distance along the bilayer normal between interpolated surface points on the opposite sides of the bilayer. In addition, this allows us to evaluate the other bilayer properties such as D_{overlap} along the xy -plane and in turn, to obtain their probability distributions besides usual ensemble averages. Specifically for D_{overlap} , the ITIM allows to identify for a chain in the monolayer (1) with $L_t^{(1)}$ its chain counterpart in the monolayer (2) with $L_t^{(2)}$. If a head of the chain is at an $[x, y]$ -position in the monolayer (1) then a head of its chain counterpart is at an $[x \pm 1r_c, y \pm 1r_c]$ -position in the monolayer (2). If the chain has no chain counterpart, D_{overlap} is not considered. If the chain has more than one chain counterparts, D_{overlap} is evaluated for each chain counterparts. The probability distributions of h_{lam} or D_{overlap} turned out to be rather useful in a proper characterisation of the gel bilayers, formed by interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases.

2.4.5 Bending Rigidity

The bending rigidity κ represents the key parameter of bilayer curvature elasticity and it can be used as input to a higher resolution model of bilayers such as an elastic membrane DPD (EM-DPD) model⁶⁴ or a meshless-membrane model with explicit solvent.⁶⁵ The elastic energy associated with the deformation of a bilayer is commonly described by the Helfrich Hamiltonian which contains several terms corresponding to different membrane deformation modes.²² The bending rigidity κ is the coefficient in the quadratic term that quantifies the energy cost of

splaying the bilayer surface from its spontaneous shape, i.e.,

$$f_s = \frac{\kappa}{2} S_t^2 \quad (21)$$

where

$$S_t = \nabla \mathbf{n} - \nabla \mathbf{N} \quad (22)$$

is the splay; \mathbf{n} is the local surfactant or FA chain director vector and \mathbf{N} is the local bilayer normal. The bending rigidity was computed using the real-space fluctuations method⁶⁶ where all implementation details can be found in the Supporting Information of Ref.⁶⁷

3 Results and Discussion

We simulated bilayers formed by CTAC and C_{16} FA (System 1), CTAC and C_{18} FA (System 2), and CTAC and C_{22} FA (System 3) in water. CTAC and C_{16} FA have the same alkyl tail lengths while C_{18} FA and C_{22} FA have longer alkyl tails than CTAC. The DPD simulations were carried out at two temperatures, $T = 1.0$ and $T = 0.7$, which correspond to the real temperatures $\simeq 330$ K and $\simeq 300$ K, respectively, and where the systems exhibit the lamellar fluid and gel phases, respectively. We considered a model, low-complexity formulation, locked on a molar ratio of 0.177 based on a 1:3.5 mass ratio of the CTAC to C_{16} FA. Table 3 summarises the number of surfactant and FA chains, n_{surf} and n_{FA} , respectively, and the number of water beads, N_w , used, corresponding to the 1:3.5 formulation. Table 3 also provides the box size for the bilayer tensionless state. Besides varying the FA length, we also studied the effects of the surfactant branching on the bilayer structures. Therefore for System 1, we replaced single-tail CTAC with double-tail DHDAC by (i) maintaining the number of surfactant tails (System 1a), $n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{DHDAC}} = n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{CTAC}}/2$, and (ii) maintaining the charge within the bilayer (System 1b), $n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{DHDAC}} = n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{CTAC}}$. The values of n_{surf} , n_{FA} , N_w , L_x , L_y , and L_z used for System 1a and System 1b are also listed in Table 3.

3.1 CTAC and C_n FA Bilayers

We begin with the effects of varying the FA length on the bilayer structures of System 1, System 2, and System 3. Table 4 summarises the integral structural characteristics of the fluid and gel bilayers, i.e., ensemble averages of the CTAC and FA overall orientational order parameters, S^{surf} and S^{FA} , respectively, the CTAC and FA chain overlaps, $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ and $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$, respectively, and the bilayer thickness, h_{lam} .

On one hand, the integral structural characteristics of the bilayers are affected by bilayer shape fluctuations and the coexistence of interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases within the bilayers but, on the other hand, they can indicate changes in the structural behaviour of the bilayers due to the change in the FA length. As expected, the values of h_{lam} for both the fluid and gel bilayers rise upon an increase of the FA length. In the gel bilayers, the CTAC and FA chains are ordered along the bilayer normal as indicated by the values of S^{surf} and S^{FA} around 0.9. In the fluid bilayers, the values of S^{surf} and S^{FA} are up to about half of those in the gel bilayers, indicating that the CTAC and FA chains become disordered. As suggested by $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$, the tendency of the FA chains

from the apposed monolayers to overlap increases with increase of the FA length and becomes more pronounced in the gel phase than in the fluid phase. This in turn explains the lower values of the h_{lam} of the gel bilayers when compared with those of the fluid bilayers. Further, as suggested by $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$, the CTAC chains from the apposed monolayers do not or hardly overlap. Therefore, $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ and $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$ indicate that the FA chains conform the primary scaffolding of the bilayers and the CTAC chains tessellate monolayers from their water-hydrophobic interface.

Figs. 2 and 3 show typical simulation snapshots and density profiles, $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$, for the fluid and gel bilayers of System 1 and System 3, respectively; the $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ are plotted for water, CI, CTAC and FA heads and tails, i.e., $\rho_w(z)$, $\rho_{\text{CI}}(z)$, $\rho_h(z)$ s, and $\rho_t(z)$ s, respectively. For System 2, bilayer snapshots and $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ are displayed in Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Information. When interpreting $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$, it is worth mentioning that the thermally excited shape fluctuations of bilayers lead to $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ that include contributions from nonplanar bilayer configurations. We see from the snapshots that the CTAC and FA chains are disordered in the fluid bilayers while they are highly ordered in the gel bilayers. In addition, the snapshots of the gel bilayers exhibit the coexistence of interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases.

As shown in Figs. 2 and 3, and Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Information, the $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ of the gel bilayers have complex shapes and are to a certain extent unsymmetrical due to the coexistence of interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases. On the contrary, the $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ of the fluid bilayers are rather symmetrical. We see that the water is excluded from the hydrophobic region of the bilayers by the strong water-CTAC and FA chain repulsion whereas both CTAC and FA heads are confined to the water-hydrophobic interfaces. For the gel bilayers, CTAC and FA $\rho_h(z)$ s exhibit either a peak followed by a tail (System 1) or two peaks (System 2 and System 3) in each monolayer which correspond to the non-interdigitated and interdigitated phases. Nevertheless, also here, the CTAC and FA heads are still confined to the water-hydrophobic interfaces of either the non-interdigitated phase or interdigitated phase. Furthermore, the peak followed by the tail in $\rho_h(z)$ of System 1 vs. two peaks in $\rho_h(z)$ s of System 2 and System 3 suggest the increasing presence of the interdigitated phase as the FA length increases. The FA $\rho_h(z)$ s further indicate an infrequent presence of the FA heads in the middle of both the fluid and gel bilayers. This suggests that the FA head can sometimes penetrate to the centre of bilayers as the FA chains can burrow their way through the bilayers emerging into the apposed monolayer – a “flip-flop” process. The CTAC chains show no flip-flop due to the strong electrostatic interactions between their head and CIs. The CIs are partially condensed at the water-hydrophobic interfaces due to CTAC head-CI pairing and partially dissolve in the water adjacent to the bilayers. For the fluid bilayers, FA $\rho_t(z)$ s suggest overlap of the FA chains in the middle of the bilayers. The overlap grows with the increase of the FA length as indicated, e.g., by the FA $\rho_t(z)$ of System 3 that becomes wider in each monolayer and has a pronounced tail towards the apposed monolayer when compared with the FA $\rho_t(z)$ of System 1. In contrast to the FA chains, the CTAC $\rho_t(z)$ of System 1 displays a minor overlap of the CTAC chains in the centre of the bilayers that completely disappears

when arriving in System 3. For the gel bilayers, the overlap/no overlap of the CTAC and FA chains depends on whether the chains belong to the interdigitated or non-interdigitated phases.

Figs. S2 to S4 of the Supplementary Information then present the corresponding bead density profiles. They elaborate the changes in the CTAC and FA overlaps/no overlaps in the fluid and gel bilayers as the FA length increases or they provide further insights into the interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases within the gel bilayers.

Fig. 4 displays the local orientational order parameters for the CTAC and FA chains, S_n^{surf} and S_n^{FA} , respectively, which characterise the orientational ordering of the individual tail bonds and its persistence through the bilayers. In the fluid bilayers, S_n^{surf} and S_n^{FA} with $S_n^{\text{surf}} > S_n^{\text{FA}}$ are below 0.5, confirming the CTAC and FA chains are in disordered state while in the gel bilayers, S_n^{surf} and S_n^{FA} reach up to 0.85, confirming the CTAC and FA chains are ordered along the bilayer normal. In the fluid bilayers, the values of S_n^{FA} are lower at the edges of the monolayers due to the mobility of the FA head at the water-hydrophobic interfaces and the higher mobility of FA tail-end beads at the interface between the monolayers. The values of S_n^{FA} rise upon any increase of the FA length as a result of the increasing overlap of the apposed monolayers. This restricts the mobility of the FA tail-end beads in the centre of the bilayers and enhances the orientational ordering of the FA chains. The values of S_n^{surf} gradually decrease from the water-hydrophobic interface towards the centre of the bilayers as the CTAC tail beads naturally become more mobile when they approach the monolayer edge in the bilayer centre. In contrast to S_n^{FA} , there is no lowering in S_n^{surf} near the water-hydrophobic interface due to the low mobility of the bulky CTAC head and due to the CTAC head-CI pairing. The values of S_n^{surf} further rise as the FA length increases in parallel with the growth in S_n^{FA} ; recall that the FA chains are primary scaffolding of the bilayer and the CTAC chains tessellate the monolayers from their water-hydrophobic interface. In the gel bilayers, the values of both S_n^{surf} and S_n^{FA} are lower at the edges of the monolayers and rather constant inside the monolayers. The lowering in S_n at both the monolayer edges is more pronounced for the FA chains than for the CTAC chains. At the monolayer edge next to the water-hydrophobic interface, this is due to the higher mobility of the FA head in comparison with the bulky CTAC head. At the monolayer edge in the centre of the bilayer, the mobility of the FA tail-end beads is higher than that of the CTAC tail-end beads since the CTAC chains are positioned further away from the monolayer edge in comparison with the FA tail-end beads, cf. $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ and $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$ in Table 4.

Fig. 5 shows the CTAC and FA chain overlap probability distributions, $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$, respectively. Recall that the ITIM method makes it possible to identify *locally* a pair of chains from the apposed monolayers and in turn, to evaluate the values of D_{overlap} via Eq. (20) for all pairs of chains from the apposed monolayers. In the fluid bilayers, the $F(D_{\text{overlap}})$ s of the FA chains, which conform the primary bilayer scaffolding, have a peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0$, and their tails towards $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} > 0$ and $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} < 0$ correspond to FA chain overlaps and no overlaps, respectively. As the FA length increases, the peak in

$F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ rises and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ has a more pronounced tail towards $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} > 0$, confirming the increase in the FA chain overlap already evident from the values of $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$ in Table 4. On the contrary, the $F(D_{\text{overlap}})$ s of the CTAC chains, which tessellate monolayers from their water-hydrophobic interface, have a peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} < 0$ with a more pronounced tail towards $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} < 0$, and indicate only minor or no CTAC chain overlap. As the FA length increases, the peak shifts towards more negative values of $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$, confirming diminishing CTAC chain overlap in the bilayer centre as already evident from the values of $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ in Table 4. In the gel bilayers, both $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ are bimodal and their peaks correspond to the non-interdigitated and interdigitated phases. The $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ s have one peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0^-$ (non-interdigitated phase) and the other at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 1$ (interdigitated phase) regardless of the FA length. The peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0^-$ is more pronounced than the peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 1$ for System 1 and the opposite becomes true when moving to System 3. This indicates that the non-interdigitated phase prevails over the interdigitated phase in System 1, this trend is reversed upon increase of the FA length and, in System 3, the interdigitated phase prevails over the non-interdigitated phase. The $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ s have one peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} < 0$ and another, minor peak around $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} \simeq 1$. The peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} < 0$ shifts towards more negative $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ and the peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}} \simeq 1$ progressively diminishes as the FA length increases. This indicates that the CTAC chains prefer to reside in the non-interdigitated phase rather than the interdigitated phase with increasing FA length.

Fig. 6 displays the bilayer thickness probability distribution, $F(h_{\text{lam}})$. For the fluid bilayers, the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ s are symmetrical, the peak position shifts to higher values of h_{lam} , proportionally with the increase of the FA length, and the peak height is independent of the FA length. For the gel bilayers, the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ s are bimodal. A peak position of $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ at lower values of h_{lam} represents the bilayer thickness of the interdigitated phase while that at higher values of h_{lam} corresponds to the bilayer thickness of the non-interdigitated phase. As the FA length increases, both peaks shift to higher values of h_{lam} , proportionally with increasing FA length.

Finally, Table 2 presents the bending rigidity κ , and its values are $(14 - 21)kT_0$ for the fluid bilayers and $(185 - 210)kT_0$ for the gel bilayers. The values of κ for both the fluid and gel bilayers tend to rise with increasing FA length and the increase correlates with growing overlap of the apposed monolayers with greater FA length. An order of magnitude higher κ s of the gel bilayers with respect to the κ s of the fluid bilayers is comparable to the experimentally determined rigidities of gel phases.^{68,69}

Finally, Supplementary Information provides videos of the simulated fluid and gel bilayers for Systems 1, 2, and 3 to demonstrate motion of CTAC and FA chains, and CIs within the bilayers and inter-lamellar water layer.

3.2 DHDAC and C₁₆FA Bilayers

We continue with the effects of the surfactant branching on the bilayer structures and compare System 1 with systems where

single-tail CTAC was replaced by double-tail DHDAC, i.e., System 1a ($n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{DHDAC}} = n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{CTAC}}/2$) and System 1b ($n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{DHDAC}} = n_{\text{surf}}^{\text{CTAC}}$). By comparing the integral structural characteristics of the bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b with those of System 1 (Table 4), we see two trends. First, the values of h_{lam} are larger for Systems 1a and 1b than for System 1 with h_{lam} s of the fluid phase greater than h_{lam} s of the gel phase. Second, the tendency of the FA chains from the apposed monolayers to overlap is lower for Systems 1a and 1b than for System 1 (cf. $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$ in Table 4), suggesting, e.g., the prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase within the gel bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b.

Figs. 7 and 8 display typical simulation snapshots and $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ for the fluid and gel bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b, respectively, and Figs. S5 and S6 of the Supplementary Information show the corresponding bead density profiles. As seen from the snapshots and close inspection of $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$, the structures of the fluid bilayers of System 1a and to a lesser extent System 1b differ qualitatively from System 1. This is further evident from a rather large value of h_{lam} in System 1a and a large value of h_{lam} in System 1b when compared with a value of h_{lam} in System 1 in Table 4. Besides the DHDAC and FA chains which form the apposed monolayers of the fluid bilayer of System 1a, there are DHDAC and FA chains that reside in the centre of the bilayer. They have their heads at the interface between the apposed monolayers with their tails interdigitated with the chains in both monolayers, thus bridging the apposed monolayers. This is accompanied with the penetration of water and CIs to the bilayer centre. For the fluid bilayer of System 1b, the number of DHDAC and FA chains together with the number of water and CI beads in the bilayer centre dropped in comparison with the fluid bilayer of System 1a but the fluid bilayer structure of System 1b still resembles that of System 1a to a certain extent. The structures of the gel bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b are rather similar as suggested by the bilayer snapshots and $\rho_{\alpha}(z)$ in Figs. 7 and 8, and Figs. S5 and S6 of the Supplementary Information. They indicate enhanced prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase within the gel bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b when compared with the gel bilayer of System 1.

Fig. 9 shows the S_n^{surf} and S_n^{FA} of Systems 1a and 1b, and compare them with those of System 1. For the DHDAC chains, S_n^{surf} was averaged over both the alkyl tails. The S_n^{FA} s suggest that in both the fluid and gel bilayers, the orientational ordering of the FA individual tail bonds and its persistence through the bilayer are almost unaffected by replacement of a single-tail CTAC by a double-tail DHDAC. In the fluid bilayers, the S_n^{surf} s of Systems 1a and 1b are very similar, they are substantially lower than the S_n^{surf} of System 1, indicating the DHDAC chains are in a rather disordered state, and, in contrast to System 1, they exhibit lowering at both edges of the monolayers. This lowering at the monolayer edge next to the water-hydrophobic interface is caused by the surfactant branching that restricts the ordering of the adjacent tail bonds along the bilayer normal. In the gel bilayers, the S_n^{surf} s of Systems 1a and 1b are substantially lower at the monolayer edge next to the water-hydrophobic interface when compared with S_n^{surf} of System 1 but then the S_n^{surf} s of Systems 1, 1a and 1b become almost identical. The substantial lowering in the

S_n^{surf} s of Systems 1a and 1b is, like in the fluid bilayer, due to the surfactant branching that restricts the ordering of adjacent tail bonds along the bilayer normal.

Fig. 10 displays $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ of Systems 1a and 1b, and compare them with those of System 1. For the fluid bilayers, both $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ of Systems 1a and 1b are very broad when compared with those of System 1 and have positions of a peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}/D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0^-$. This indicates significant shape fluctuations of the fluid bilayers and high chain disorder within the fluid bilayers of Systems 1a and 1b. For the gel bilayers, both $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}})$ and $F(D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}})$ of Systems 1a and 1b have a dominant peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}/D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0^-$ (non-interdigitated phase) and a small or no peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}/D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 1$ (interdigitated phase). When comparing Systems 1a and 1b with System 1, the peak at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}/D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 0^-$ is higher and that at $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}/D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}} \simeq 1$ smaller or negligible, confirming the enhanced prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase in Systems 1a and 1b.

Fig. 11 shows the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ of Systems 1a and 1b, and compare it with that for System 1. For the fluid bilayers, the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ s of Systems 1a and 1b, in contrast to the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ of System 1, are highly unsymmetrical, confirming once again the significant shape fluctuations in the fluid bilayers. For the gel bilayers, the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ s of Systems 1a and 1b, similarly to the $F(h_{\text{lam}})$ of System 1, are bimodal and the peak at lower values of h_{lam} corresponds to the bilayer thickness of the interdigitated phase while the peak at higher values of h_{lam} represents the bilayer thickness of the non-interdigitated phase. The positions of both the peaks are roughly at the same h_{lam} s for all three systems but the peak heights differ. The non-interdigitated phase peak dominates over the interdigitated phase peak in Systems 1a and 1b, confirming once again the enhanced prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase in Systems 1a and 1b when compared with System 1.

Table 2 compares the κ s of Systems 1a and 1b with the κ of System 1. For the fluid bilayers, the values of κ are about $(8 - 10)kT_0$ for Systems 1a and 1b, which is about 2/3 of the κ of System 1 due to the disordered state of the DHDAC chains, cf. Fig. 9. For the gel bilayers, the values of κ of Systems 1a and 1b are about the same or slightly lower than the κ of System 1 due to two opposing effects: higher rigidity of the double-tail amphiphilic chains in comparison with that of the single-tail amphiphilic chains⁶⁶ vs. lowering of the FA chains overlap, and in turn non-interdigitation in Systems 1a and 1b when compared with System 1.

Finally, Supplementary Information presents videos of the simulated fluid and gel bilayers for Systems 1a and 1b to demonstrate motion of DHDAC and FA chains, and CIs within the bilayers and inter-lamellar water layer.

4 Summary and Conclusion

Dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) simulations were employed to study the structure of the fluid and gel bilayers, self-assembled by cationic surfactants and fatty alcohols (FAs) in water. The fluid bilayers are a key determinant for the formation of the lamel-

lar gel networks – creamy formulations extensively used in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals – while the gel bilayers are the fundamental building blocks of the lamellar gel networks and their structures determine the macroscopic properties of the lamellar gel networks. Quaternary ammonium surfactant CTAC combined with FAs with an alkyl tail equal to the CTAC alkyl tail (C_{16} FA) or greater than the CTAC alkyl tail (C_{18} FA and C_{22} FA) in water were considered. Besides varying the FA length, we also explored the effect of the surfactant branching on the bilayer structures and replaced the single-tail CTAC by the double-tail DHDAC. A model conditioner formulation with the FA concentration greater than that of the surfactant was considered.

The generic DPD force field of Anderson et al.^{26,27} developed for amphiphilic molecules was used where we parametrised the interaction parameters for charged DPD beads and also added the bond-bond repulsive interactions to avoid topology violations.³¹ In contrast to generic Flory-Huggins-type DPD models,³⁴ the generic DPD force field with our new charged-bead interaction parameters allows quantitative prediction of self-assembly in surfactant-based systems.²⁷⁻³⁰

Overall, the DPD simulations predicted that the FA chains conformed the primary scaffolding of the bilayers and the surfactant chains tessellated monolayers of the bilayers from their water-hydrophobic interface. The water was excluded from the hydrophobic region of the bilayers, the surfactant and FA heads together with counter-ions were confined to the water-hydrophobic interfaces, and interdigitation/non-interdigitation of the surfactant and FA tails, forming the apposed monolayers of the bilayers, was primarily affected by the FA length and to a lesser extent by surfactant branching. The FA chains exhibited flip-flop where the FA chains burrowed their way through the bilayers and emerged in the apposed monolayer. The gel bilayers were composed by both the interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases.

The notion and evidence for the degree of interdigitation in the gel phase was initially proposed and reported by Vincent and Skoulios,⁷⁰ whose experiments using SAXS found a linear dependence between d -spacing and gel-phase concentration. Vincent and Skoulios calculated the bilayer thickness and the lateral chain length [cf. Eq. (20)], and measured dependence of the d -spacing on concentration. At high gel-phase concentrations, d -spacing drops linearly below the bilayer thickness suggesting interdigitation. The lateral chain length [cf. Eq. (20)] is determined at the intercept extrapolated from this dependence. In practice, the experimental evidence at its best offers an average notion of the degree of interdigitation over the scattering volume that X-ray beams diffracts from.⁷⁰ The DPD offers a detailed description of the degree of interdigitation, admittedly over the limited volume of the box, but with the additional insights that reveal the coexistence of the interdigitated and non-interdigitated phases, information unavailable from experiments.

The coexistence of the non-interdigitated and interdigitated gel phases was also observed, both in mesoscopic simulations^{21,25} and experimentally,^{71,72} for lipid bilayers with incorporation of small amphiphilic molecules such as alcohols at the bilayer interface. A coexistence region of the non-interdigitated and interdigitated phases exists between low and high alcohol concentra-

Table 2 System composition and system notation along with simulation values of the bending rigidity κ for the fluid ($T = 1.0$) and gel ($T = 0.7$) bilayers; x_{surf} and x_{FA} are the surfactant and FA mole fractions, respectively, w_{surf} and w_{FA} are the surfactant and FA mass fractions, respectively, k is the Boltzmann constant, $T_0 = 330$ K is the reference temperature, and molecular weights: $M_w^{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2} = 36.03$ g/mol, $M_w^{\text{CTAC}} = 320.0$ g/mol, $M_w^{\text{DHDAC}} = 530.39$ g/mol, $M_w^{\text{C}_{16}\text{FA}} = 242.44$ g/mol, $M_w^{\text{C}_{18}\text{FA}} = 270.49$ g/mol, and $M_w^{\text{C}_{22}\text{FA}} = 326.61$ g/mol. The simulation uncertainties of κ are given in the last digits as subscripts; i.e., for example, $\text{XXX}.X_{y_y} \equiv \text{XXX}.X \pm y.y$.

System	Notation	x_{surf}	x_{FA}	w_{surf}	w_{FA}	$\kappa/(kT_0)$	
						Fluid Bilayer	Gel Bilayer
water/CTAC/C ₁₆ FA	System 1	$1.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.94 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$10.76 \cdot 10^{-2}$	13.9 ₄	189.7 ₄₅
water/CTAC/C ₁₈ FA	System 2	$1.93 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.95 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$12.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	14.1 ₄	185.7 ₄₄
water/CTAC/C ₁₈ FA	System 3	$2.01 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.97 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$14.66 \cdot 10^{-2}$	20.7 ₆	208.2 ₅₀
water/DHDAC/C ₁₆ FA	System 1a	$0.98 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.46 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.95 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$13.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$	10.2 ₃	189.8 ₄₂
water/DHDAC/C ₁₆ FA	System 1b	$1.96 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$9.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.91 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$10.84 \cdot 10^{-2}$	8.5 ₃	175.6 ₄₀

Table 3 The number of surfactant and FA chains, n_{surf} and n_{FA} , respectively, and the number of water beads, N_w , along with the box lengths, L_x , L_y , and L_z , which correspond to the bilayer tensionless state at $T = 1.0$ and 0.7 , and which were used in the DPD simulations of this work.

System	n_{surf}	n_{FA}	N_w	$T = 1.0$			$T = 0.7$		
				L_x	L_y	L_z	L_x	L_y	L_z
System 1	478	2310	124617	36.468	36.468	37.548	36.420	36.420	36.903
System 2	478	2310	122307	36.464	36.464	37.544	36.320	36.320	37.107
System 3	478	2310	117687	35.058	35.058	40.595	36.412	36.412	36.895
System 1a	239	2310	100003	30.783	30.783	44.004	33.539	33.539	36.305
System 1b	478	2310	120793	36.293	36.293	38.047	35.954	35.954	37.970

tions. At low alcohol concentrations, lipid-alcohol systems typically form non-interdigitated gel bilayers. At high alcohol concentrations, alcohol molecules promote interdigitation of lipid chains. Here, the alcohol molecules replace the interfacial water and create lateral space between the head groups, leading to voids in the hydrophobic core. These voids are energetically unfavourable and thus the lipid-alcohol system minimises its energy by the formation of an interdigitated phase. Due to interdigitation, the system gains energy because of the stronger interaction in the interdigitated phase compared to the non-interdigitated phase, and increases the entropy by replacing the water molecules at the interface by alcohol molecules. Since the tail ends of the alcohol molecules shield the tail ends of the lipids from the interfacial water, the energy cost in the formation of the interdigitated phase is further lowered.^{21,25} Then, the coexistence of the non-interdigitated and interdigitated gel phases in the lipid-alcohol systems is due to an inhomogeneous distribution of the alcohol molecules in the bilayer. If alcohol molecules concentrate in certain regions of the bilayer a mosaic pattern of localised interdigitation can be formed.^{71,72} Based on our DPD simulation results, the nature of the coexistence of the non-interdigitated and interdigitated gel phases in our surfactant and FA systems can be explained in an analogous way as in the lipid-alcohol systems by considering that the FA chains play a role of lipids and the surfactant chains act as alcohol molecules.

Further, the interdigitated gel phase is stabilised for lipids with longer hydrophobic tails, consistently with the simulation and experimental results.^{58,73} Since the interdigitated phase is more closely packed than the non-interdigitated phase, the interaction energy is greater. This energy gain is proportional to the number of carbon atoms in the lipid chains and thus interdigitation becomes energetically more favourable for longer chains. Analogously to the lipid systems, the interdigitated gel phase in our surfactant and FA systems is stabilised and prevailed over the non-interdigitated phase upon increase of the FA tail length.

By varying the FA length, i.e., moving from the system of the CTAC/C₁₆FA in water to the system of the CTAC/C₂₂FA in water, the DPD simulations indicated the following:

- The bilayer thickness of the fluid bilayers rose with increasing FA length.
- The overlap of the FA chains in the centre of the fluid bilayers was greater when the FA length increased.
- The overlap of the surfactant chains in the centre of the fluid bilayers completely diminished upon any increase of the FA length.
- The bending rigidity of the fluid bilayers grew with the increase of the FA length as a result of the greater FA chain overlap.
- The bilayer thickness of both the non-interdigitated and interdigitated phases within the gel bilayers rose when the FA length was increased.
- The non-interdigitated phase prevailed over the interdigitated phase within the gel bilayer consisting of C₁₆FA chains. This reversed upon FA length increase and the interdigitated phase prevailed over the non-interdigitated phase within the gel bilayer composed of C₂₂FA chains.
- The surfactant chains of the gel bilayers preferred to reside in the non-interdigitated phase rather than in the interdigitated phase.
- The bending rigidity of the gel bilayers was an order of magnitude higher than that of the fluid bilayers and tended to grow when the FA length increased. This is due to the enhanced prevalence of the interdigitated phase over the non-interdigitated phase upon FA length increase.

Fig. 2 The bilayer snapshots and density profiles of water, Cl, and CTAC and FA heads and tails for the fluid (left column) and gel (right column) bilayers of System 1; z denotes coordinates across the bilayers. All density profiles except the water density profile are reduced by the number density of liquid water $\rho_w = 3$. In the bilayer snapshots, the blue spheres represent Cl, the red and cyan spheres depict CTAC head and tail beads, respectively, and the yellow and green spheres represent FA head and tail beads, respectively. Water beads are suppressed for the sake of clarity.

By introducing the surfactant branching, i.e., considering the DHDAC/C₁₆FA in water with either the number of surfactant tails or the charge within the bilayer fixed, the DPD simulations predicted the following:

- The structure of the fluid bilayers changed qualitatively with respect to the fluid bilayer of the system CTAC/C₁₆FA in water. It was characterised by the presence of surfactant and FA chains along with water beads and partially-condensed counter-ions at the interface between the apposed monolayers. These surfactant and FA chains interdigitated with the chains in both monolayers and bridged the apposed monolayers.
- The gel bilayers exhibited enhanced prevalence of the non-interdigitated phase over the interdigitated phase when compared with the gel bilayer of the CTAC/C₁₆FA system in water.
- The bending rigidity of the fluid bilayers lowered with respect to that of the CTAC/C₁₆FA system in water, due to disordered arrangement of the DHDAC chains. The bending

rigidity of the gel bilayers was about the same or slightly decreased when compared with that of the CTAC/C₁₆FA system in water, due to two opposing effects: higher rigidity of the double-tail DHDAC in comparison with that of the single-tail CTAC vs. increasing of non-interdigitation in comparison with single-tail CTAC chains.

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Fig. 3 The bilayer snapshots and density profiles of water, Cl, and CTAC and FA heads and tails for the fluid (left column) and gel (right column) bilayers of System 3; z denotes coordinates across the bilayers. All density profiles except the water density profile are reduced by the number density of liquid water $\rho_w = 3$. In the bilayer snapshots, the blue spheres represent Cl, the red and cyan spheres depict CTAC head and tail beads, respectively, and the yellow and green spheres represent FA head and tail beads, respectively. Water beads are suppressed for the sake of clarity.

A Charged Beads Nonbonded Interactions

There has been no systematic approach to parametrise the non-bonded interaction parameters, R_{ij} and a_{ij} , for charged beads in DPD,⁵³ i.e., the surfactants head $h1 \equiv [(CH_3)_3N^+CH_2]$ and $h2 \equiv [(CH_3)_2N^+]$ with $q_h = +1e$, and counter-ion $CI \equiv [Cl^-]$ with $q_{CI} = -1e$ in this work. We thus followed the pragmatic approach of Anderson et al.²⁷ which first assigns $R_{h1,h1} = (V_{m,h1}/V_{m,(H_2O)_2})^{1/3}$ and $R_{h2,h2} = (V_{m,h2}/V_{m,(H_2O)_2})^{1/3}$ with $V_{m,h1} = 91.5 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ and $V_{m,h2} = 56.2 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ determined by the group-contribution method of Durchschlag and Zipper.⁴⁰ The values of $R_{h1,j}$ and of $R_{h2,j}$ are then given by the arithmetic mixing rule as $R_{h1,j} = (R_{h1,h1} + R_{jj})/2$ and $R_{h2,j} = (R_{h2,h2} + R_{jj})/2$, respectively. In addition, the CI is treated as the water bead with $q_{CI} = -1e$. Second, as R_{ij} varies, the approach sets $a_{ij}R_{ij}^3 = 25$ for all interactions involving two charged DPD beads or one charged DPD bead and water bead, which in turn yields values of a_{ij} (the values of R_{ij} are already known). Third, for the values of a_{ij} between the surfactants head $h1$ or $h2$, and surfactant and FA uncharged beads, the approach considers $h1$ or $h2$ as a head bead $[CH_2OCH_2]$ of nonionic surfactants alkyl-poly(ethylene oxide) (C_nE_m) with the

values of a_{ij} given by the transferable DPD FF.²⁶ All nonbonded interaction parameters for the charged beads are then listed in Table 1.

Similarly as Anderson et al.,²⁷ we justified the reliability of our determined R_{ij} and a_{ij} parameters for the charged DPD beads by simulating the CMC of the $C_{12}TAB$ surfactant without the bond-bond repulsive potential (6). The $C_{12}TAB$ has the identical charged head as CTAC but $C_{12}TAB$ is shorter than CTAC, which eases simulation of the CMC. In addition, the experimental values of its CMC are readily available.⁴⁴ To estimate the CMC of ionic surfactants in DPD simulations, the approach of Neimark et al.⁷⁴ was employed. We performed DPD simulations of the aqueous $C_{12}TAB$ solution with variance of the total surfactant concentration, C_t . From the DPD simulations, the unimer surfactant concentration, C_f , was determined using the clustering algorithm,¹⁷ which expressed the relation between C_f and C_t using the semiempirical theory of Sanders et al.^{75,76} as

$$\log(C_f) = (1 + \alpha) \log(C_{CMC}) - \alpha \log \left[\frac{(1 + \alpha)(C_t - C_f) + C_f}{1 - V_m C_t} \right] \quad (A1)$$

Table 4 The surfactant and FA overall orientational order parameters, S^{surf} and S^{FA} , respectively, the surfactant and FA chain overlap, $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$ and $D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$, respectively, and the bilayer thickness, h_{lam} , for the fluid ($T = 1.0$) and gel ($T = 0.7$) bilayers. The simulation uncertainties are given in the last digits as subscripts; i.e., for example, $XX.X_y \equiv XX.X \pm 0.y$.

System	Fluid Bilayer ($T = 1.0$)					Gel Bilayer ($T = 0.7$)				
	S^{surf}	S^{FA}	$D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$	$D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$	h_{lam} (Å)	S^{surf}	S^{FA}	$D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{surf}}$	$D_{\text{overlap}}^{\text{FA}}$	h_{lam} (Å)
System 1	0.43 ₂	0.34 ₂	-0.82 ₃	-0.21 ₁	41.0 ₅	0.88 ₃	0.90 ₃	-0.09 ₇	0.27 ₂	38.7 ₄
System 2	0.46 ₂	0.38 ₂	-0.99 ₄	-0.14 ₁	44.2 ₆	0.85 ₃	0.88 ₃	-0.39 ₂	0.31 ₂	42.5 ₅
System 3	0.54 ₂	0.49 ₂	-1.50 ₆	-0.05 ₁	54.3 ₈	0.85 ₃	0.92 ₃	-0.77 ₃	0.42 ₃	48.7 ₆
System 1a	0.19 ₁	0.25 ₁	-0.51 ₂	-0.64 ₂	54.3 ₈	0.87 ₃	0.93 ₃	-0.04 ₄	-0.05 ₄	43.5 ₅
System 1b	0.23 ₁	0.29 ₂	-0.41 ₂	-0.49 ₂	46.4 ₆	0.88 ₃	0.92 ₃	-0.07 ₅	-0.06 ₄	44.2 ₅

Fig. 4 The surfactant (top) and FA (bottom) local orientational order parameters for the fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayers of Systems 1, 2, and 3. The values of the orientational order parameter close to 0.25 correspond to random chain orientations while those close to 1 indicate that the chains align along the bilayer normal.

Fig. 5 The surfactant (top) and FA (bottom) chain overlap probability distributions for the fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayers of Systems 1, 2, and 3. At the chain overlap, D_{overlap} , equal to 0, the chains touch tail-to-tail, at $D_{\text{overlap}} < 0$, the chains separate further apart, and at $D_{\text{overlap}} > 0$, the chains overlap.

Fig. 6 The fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayer thickness probability distributions of Systems 1, 2, and 3.

In Eq. (A1), V_m is the molar volume of surfactant equal to $255.6 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$, α is the degree of association of the CIs with the head groups of the surfactants forming the micelles, and C_{CMC} is the concentration of CMC. We treated both α and C_{CMC} as fitting parameters. Fig. 12 shows the DPD simulation values of C_f as a function of C_i obtained using both the Gaussian and exponential smeared charged distributions together with the fit of the DPD data to Eq. (A1), and the experimental value of $C_{\text{CMC}}^{\text{exp}} \simeq 16 \text{ mM}$ at 25°C .⁴⁴ The DPD simulations with the exponential smeared charged distribution was carried out using DL_MESO software package.⁷⁷ The fits yield $\alpha = 0.70$ and $C_{\text{CMC}}^{\text{DPD}} = 8.3 \text{ mM}$ for the Gaussian smeared charged distribution, and $C_{\text{CMC}}^{\text{DPD}} = 7.7 \text{ mM}$ for the exponential smeared charged distribution. The (dis)agreement between $C_{\text{CMC}}^{\text{DPD}}$ and $C_{\text{CMC}}^{\text{exp}}$ is acceptable given the state of the art in DPD simulations of ionic molecules.

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Fig. 7 The bilayer snapshots and density profiles of water, CI, and DHDAC and FA heads and tails for the fluid (left column) and gel (right column) bilayers of System 1a; z denotes coordinates across the bilayers. All density profiles except the water density profile are reduced by the number density of liquid water $\rho_w = 3$. In the bilayer snapshots, the blue spheres represent CI, the red and cyan spheres depict DHDAC head and tail beads, respectively, and the yellow and green spheres represent FA head and tail beads, respectively. Water beads are suppressed for the sake of clarity.

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Fig. 8 The bilayer snapshots and density profiles of water, CI, and DHDAC and FA heads and tails for the fluid (left column) and gel (right column) bilayers of System 1b; z denotes coordinates across the bilayers. All density profiles except the water density profile are reduced by the number density of liquid water $\rho_w = 3$. In the bilayer snapshots, the blue spheres represent CI, the red and cyan spheres depict DHDAC head and tail beads, respectively, and the yellow and green spheres represent FA head and tail beads, respectively. Water beads are suppressed for the sake of clarity.

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Fig. 9 The surfactant (top) and FA (bottom) local orientational order parameters for the fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayers of Systems 1, 1a, and 1b. The values of the orientational order parameter close to 0.25 correspond to random chain orientations while those close to 1 indicate that the chains align along the bilayer normal.

Fig. 10 The surfactant (top) and FA (bottom) chain overlap probability distributions for the fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayers of Systems 1, 1a, and 1b. At the chain overlap, D_{overlap} , equal to 0, the chains touch tail-to-tail, at $D_{\text{overlap}} < 0$, the chains separate further apart, and at $D_{\text{overlap}} > 0$, the chains overlap.

Fig. 11 The fluid (dashed lines) and gel (solid lines) bilayer thickness probability distributions of Systems 1, 1a, and 1b.

Fig. 12 The unimer surfactant concentration, C_f , as a function of the total surfactant concentration, C_t , for the aqueous C_{12} TAB solution from the DPD simulations of this work. (a) The Gaussian smeared charge distribution: $C_{CMC}^{DPD} = 8.3$ mM; (b) The exponential smeared charge distribution: $C_{CMC}^{DPD} = 7.7$ mM.